

THE IMPORTANCE OF GRAMMAR IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract

The Word Grammar implies different things to different people. To the average person, it refers to the correctness or incorrectness of the language he or she speaks. To a high school student, it entails analyzing and categorizing sentences. Grammar knowledge assists students in correcting errors and improving written work. Only by unconscious assimilation can a person accurately learn a new language. When our linguistic habits fail us, grammar is a reliable source of reference. As a result, grammar is critical for the pupil. My goal in writing this paper is to draw the attention of both the language teacher and the learner to the true utility of grammar in teaching.

Key words: grammar, language learning, written language, normativity, functionality

INTRODUCTION

Grammar has long been studied as a supplement to rhetoric in ancient Greece and Rome, and as one of the seven liberal arts in medieval education. Although the means for studying grammar have changed substantially in recent years, the motivations for studying grammar have stayed mostly unchanged. One of the most logical solutions to the topic of why grammar matters can be found in a position statement on grammar instruction in American schools. Grammar is crucial because it is language that allows us to discourse about language. Grammar describes the various sorts of words and word combinations that comprise sentences in any language. Even as children, we can put sentences together—we can all perform grammar. However, learning about grammar entails being able to discuss how sentences are constructed, as well as the many sorts of words and word groupings that comprise sentences. And understanding grammar provides a window into the human mind and our astonishingly sophisticated mental capabilities. People associate grammar with errors and correctness. But knowing about grammar also helps us understand what makes sentences and paragraphs clear and interesting and precise. Grammar can be part of literature discussions when we and our students closely read the sentences in poetry and stories. And knowing about grammar means finding out that all languages and all dialects follow grammatical patterns.

Consider the following answers from various English and education experts on why grammar matters: " "Much could be advanced in terms of the utility and value

of studying Grammar and composition concepts in order to urge young people to pursue this field of study... Many of the differences in opinion among men, as well as the conflicts, contentions, and alienations of heart that have too often resulted from such divisions, have been caused by a lack of sufficient skill in the connotation and meaning of words, and by a persistent misapplication of language."

"Language studies is a component of broad knowledge. We study the complicated workings of the human body to better comprehend ourselves; for the same reason, we should study the magnificent intricacy of human language..."

"If you understand the nature of language, you will recognize the source of your linguistic prejudices and may be able to moderate them; you will also be able to more clearly assess linguistic issues of public concern, such as concerns about the state of the language or what to do about immigrant education. A more evident practical application of studying the English language is that it can help you use the language more effectively."

Knowing grammar will help second language learners and native speakers understand distinct English dialects in an international context. Even though we don't want to admit it, when someone speaks perfectly, we subconsciously hold them in higher regard and believe they have more authority than someone who struggles with the language. Keep the grammar point presentation brief, no more than 10 or 15 minutes.

Make it a point to emphasize when it will be used so that pupils are fully aware of its purpose. Following instruction, perform a carefully supervised exercise for accuracy followed by a free activity to practice fluency. When it comes time for a grammar class, communicating the overarching objective of grammar will also help to get pupils on your side. Grammar is the structural foundation of our ability to communicate. The more we understand how language works, the better we can assess the meaning and efficacy of how we and others use language. It can aid in the development of precision, the detection of ambiguity, and the utilization of the richness of expression accessible in English. And it can assist everyone — not just English teachers, but teachers of every subject, because all teaching is ultimately about grasping meaning.

Grammar is an important term in general language theory, although a detailed examination of how grammar has been and can be understood is outside the scope of this article. Theoretical, (traditional) descriptive/reference, and (traditional) pedagogical grammars are commonly distinguished by writers on the subject (Aarts 2006; Kachru 2010; Leech 1994; Odlin 1994; Tonkyn 1994). In general, pedagogical grammars appear to be about "usefulness rather than the

philosophy of adequacy or simplicity stated for pure grammars" (Chalker 1994; Corder 1988; Taylor 2008). (Spolsky 1978: 5).

In other words, grammars serve as learning aids rather than being objects of knowledge in and of themselves (Corder 1988; Kachru 2010; Rutherford 1987, 1988; for more on grammars produced for other practical goals, see Leitner & Graustein 1989). 3. The descriptive linguist's role is to describe and analyze structures and norms without regard for didactic or pedagogical issues (Achard 2004; Kachru 2010; Nikula 2003; Rutherford 1987; Wilkins 1974).

Furthermore, theoretical grammars frequently aim to prove or support a specific theoretical view on language and/or grammar or a descriptive ideal, whereas pedagogical grammars can afford to be more eclectic and use insights from different types of grammatical description based on practical learning goals and practical experience. Although pedagogical grammars are not intended for the same reasons as theoretical grammars, it appears that the substance of pedagogical grammars is or should be informed by developments in general linguistic description, and that at least some teachers are aware of linguistic changes. Of course, they cannot be theoretical, and educational grammars are also descriptive in certain ways (see Dirven 1989; Hasan & Perrett 1994; Leech 1994; Leitner & Graustein 1989; Tomlin 1994; Westney 1994; Wilkins 1974).

If, as Leech (1994) suggests, "teacher's grammar" (theoretical and descriptive) is located somewhere between "academic grammar" (theoretical and descriptive) and "grammar for the learner" (practical, selective, task-oriented, etc.), there appears to be at least an indirect link between folk and expert views on language (see Coupland & Jaworski 2004). Nonetheless, it appears plausible to infer that grammar or grammars are typically perceived as normative formal norms codified in books and/or presented by teachers from a folk linguistic (i.e. non-linguist) standpoint (see Odlin 1994). In other words, grammar is regarded to be an explicit metalinguistic description of a language, which is understood as an imagined singularity such as "Spanish," "Russian," "Norwegian Bokml" and so on. It appears that people frequently associate grammar with grammar books and institutional language acquisition. The efficacy of an explicit concentration on grammar is debated, and some students prefer 'communicating' as a method of learning. Obviously, it is possible to communicate without using current structural aspects of a language (see Cook 1989; Nikula 2003; Tonkyn 1994). The belief that you may communicate without language stems from a perceived conflict between lexis and grammar, in which grammar is assigned a reduced communicative and interactional significance. Lexis and grammar, on the other hand, share communicative obligations and should not be considered

independent entities (see Boers & Lindstromberg 2006; Broccias 2008; Langacker 2008; Widdowson 1988).

CONCLUSION

To sum up, grammar is the heart of language and its role is important. The attitudes toward grammar in turn exhibited by the majority of students should be welcomed by teachers who believe that employing grammar aids more efficient language learning. Still, grammar appears to require some demythologizing and should be viewed as just another semiotic resource for communication.

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